

FinnAffect: An affective speech corpus for spontaneous Finnish

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ABSTRACT

Affective expression plays a major role in everyday spoken and written language. In order to study how affect is expressed by Finnish language users in day-to-day life, data consisting of samples from naturalistic and unscripted contexts is required. The present work describes the first spontaneous speech corpus for Finnish with affect-related annotations, containing 12,000 transcribed samples of unscripted speech paired with continuous-valued scores of valence and arousal marked by five native Finnish speakers. We first describe the creation of the corpus, based on combining speech samples from three large-scale Finnish speech corpora, from which we chose samples for annotation using an active learning-based affect mining approach. We then report characteristics of the resulting corpus and annotation consistency, followed by speech emotion recognition (SER) experiments with several classifiers and regression models to test the feasibility of the corpus for SER system development and evaluation. Annotation analyses reveal mean Pearson correlations between annotator scores and the mean of all annotators to be $\rho_{mean} = 0.856$ for valence and $\rho_{mean} = 0.898$ for arousal. The SER experiments on discretized labels result in an average unweighted average recall (UAR) of 0.458 for ternary valence classification and 0.719 for binary arousal classification using a fine-tuned ExHuBERT model for valence prediction and a support vector machine (SVM) classifier for arousal prediction, reaching comparable levels to those reported earlier for spontaneous speech. For the regression task, concordance correlation coefficients of 0.270 and 0.689 were obtained for valence and arousal, respectively, when using a WavLM-based model trained on MSP-Podcast corpus and fine-tuned on the target data. Overall, the analyses suggest that the corpus provides a feasible basis for later study on affective expression in spontaneous Finnish.

1. Introduction

Spoken language contains affective (emotional or emotion-inducing) information, which is conveyed in speech as both segmental and suprasegmental variation, as well as in the lexical, morphological, and syntactic properties of the expressed linguistic content. The affective cues are ultimately perceived by the listener through subjective interpretations. Human emotional experiences seem to have cross-cultural similarity to some degree (Prinz, 2004; Russell et al., 1989; Eilola and Havelka, 2010; Sianipar et al., 2016), but the expression and perception of affective states through language also depend on cultural social conventions (Wierzbicka, 1986; Evans and Levinson, 2009).

Although affective expression is part of everyday conversational communication, there is relatively little existing research on the expression and perception of affect in spontaneous speech, not to mention the potential variation of affect expression between individual speakers, for example, in relation to their age or dialectal background. The scarcity of such studies becomes even more apparent when working with less-resourced languages, such as Finnish. To study the specific

nature of affective expression in everyday spoken Finnish, a dataset of spontaneous Finnish speech with affect-related annotations would be required. However, to date, there has not been a representative corpus of spontaneous Finnish speech with affective labels available, limiting the extent to which affect has been studied in spoken Finnish beyond acted speech (e.g., Airas and Alku 2006, Seppänen et al. 2003) or corpora from very specific communicative contexts (Vaaras et al., 2023).

To address the need for affective speech data for Finnish, this paper describes the creation and quality estimation of the first affective speech corpus of spontaneous Finnish language using automated sample discovery (affect mining) and active learning (AL) to support speech annotation efforts. The presented study was conducted in two separate parts.

In part one, we introduce and analyze a representative corpus of spontaneous speech samples paired with affect-related labels that enables future research of affective expression in spontaneous Finnish. We utilize three large-scale, non-scripted Finnish speech datasets as a

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basis, from which samples are automatically selected for annotation. Together with the corpus properties, we describe and examine the used annotation scheme and sampling methods as means for finding samples for annotation with rich variation from the source datasets that do not contain the required metadata related to the phenomena of affective speech.

In part two, we test the feasibility of the corpus for studying affective properties of speech by training and testing three different machine learning algorithms for both SER classification and regression tasks. The goal of the SER experiments is to examine the quality and consistency of the annotations from a machine learning perspective, hence producing further information on the feasibility of the corpus as a basis for the study of affect in Finnish.

2. Related works

Speech emotion datasets are typically collected by hiring professional actors to produce emotionally varying utterances in a controlled recording setting (e.g., [Livingstone and Russo, 2018](#)), stimulating two or more research participants to converse in a controlled context and recording the induced interactions (e.g., [Busso et al., 2008](#)), or collecting spontaneous speech in a completely uncontrolled setting from different media or crowdsourcing platforms (e.g., [Lotfian and Busso, 2019](#); see [Rathi and Tripathy 2024](#), [George and Muhamed Ilyas 2024](#) for recent reviews). The trade-off when building these types of datasets is typically between the level of naturally occurring affective expression present in the captured speech (i.e., representativeness of the data) and the degree to which the dataset contains accurate information about the affect present in the recorded speech. Although controlled in expressive content (comprehensively covering a broad range of expression styles), acted speech is often considered unnatural and overemphasized compared to everyday speech. Collection of elicited conversational audio, while often more naturalistic in expressive content, is still time-consuming and costly ([Lotfian and Busso, 2019](#)), as data collection requires acquiring participants to attend specifically planned recording sessions. This sets limits to both the volume of data that can be recorded and the amount of individual speakers contributing their specific style of expression to the collection of data used to build the corpora. Furthermore, annotating spontaneous and unscripted speech data is time-consuming, and manual selection of expression-rich samples from a large amount of spontaneous speech data requires substantial effort.

In the context of Finnish, several large corpora of spontaneous Finnish speech are available ([Moisio et al., 2022](#); [University of Helsinki, 2014](#); [Tampere University, 2023](#)). These datasets combined contain thousands of hours of unscripted speech. However, they do not contain affect-related annotations through which affective language could be examined. Nevertheless, datasets containing rich and representative spontaneous Finnish paired with affect-related labels are needed to advance both the linguistic research and speech technology related to speech emotion recognition (SER) in the Finnish language.

To our knowledge, only a few Finnish affective speech datasets exist, most of which contain acted speech samples with discrete emotion labels validated by separate human listeners ([Seppänen et al., 2003](#); [Airas and Alku, 2006](#); [Waaramaa et al., 2008](#)). These datasets have later been used in testing automatic discrimination of emotions from spoken Finnish based on statistical classification ([Toivanen et al., 2004](#)) as well as studying the emotional valence and activation levels in vowel segments ([Waaramaa et al., 2010](#)), the perceptual and acoustical dimensions of the emotional conveyance of the phone [a] ([Toivanen et al., 2006](#)), and studying the role of the different prosodic variables in the expression and perception of emotions ([Waaramaa et al., 2006](#)). Similarly, [Waaramaa \(2015\)](#) collected a speech emotion dataset consisting of nonsense utterances, aiming to investigate the level of universality in the perception of basic emotions. In terms of spontaneous Finnish speech data, the only existing speech emotion corpus ([Vaaras et al., 2023](#)) consists of child-centered speech recorded in a hospital

environment, differing from the typical everyday contexts in which most linguistic expression appears. While the dataset of [Vaaras et al. \(2023\)](#) is not freely available for research due to data privacy reasons, their study shows that spontaneous speech data can be utilized in the deployment and evaluation of SER systems.

Beyond the Finnish language, there are several prominent speech emotion datasets used to build and test SER classifiers (see, e.g., [Livingstone and Russo, 2018](#); [Busso et al., 2008](#); [Burkhardt et al., 2005](#)). However, corpora containing spontaneous speech with affect-related labels and a large number of speakers are scarce (although see, e.g., [Lotfian and Busso, 2019](#)), especially so for smaller languages such as Finnish. This scarcity underlines the need for a broader representation of languages, language users, and contexts in the study of affective expression. Therefore, understanding of the perception and expression of affect in spontaneous speech is still lacking for many languages, and for Finnish in particular.

Finally, one common use for speech emotion datasets is building SER classifiers and regression models, which can be utilized in different product applications as well as in basic linguistic research. Tackling SER tasks has been a recurring topic in speech technology-related research since the 1970s, consisting of various data processing and modeling methods (see, e.g., [Williamson, 1978](#); [Dellaert et al., 1996](#); [Scherer, 2000](#); [Lee and Narayanan, 2005](#); [Schuller et al., 2009, 2013](#)). The current state-of-the-art results in SER have been obtained by fine-tuning Transformer models with affective labels after they have been pre-trained with large unannotated speech corpora (such as [Baevski et al., 2020](#); [Hsu et al., 2021](#)). The latest state-of-the-art results using this approach were achieved by [Amiriparian et al. \(2024a\)](#), who introduced a new multilingual, multicultural speech emotion corpus (EmoSet++) together with their SER model ExHuBERT. In addition, non-neural network-based classification algorithms, such as support vector machines (SVMs), are still applied in SER with good results (e.g., [Vaaras et al., 2023](#)). For testing the usability of the corpus introduced in the current study, we use both ExHuBERT and SVM architectures as well as a WavLM-based regression model and a support vector regression (SVR) algorithm for SER experiments and compare the results to some of the latest results achieved in the field of SER.

3. The creation of the FinnAffect corpus

This section introduces the FinnAffect Corpus, a dataset of spontaneous speech samples in Finnish with 12,000 speech samples annotated for valence and arousal by human annotators. The corpus was compiled from three different unscripted speech datasets. A high-level description of the dataset creation process steps is shown in [Fig. 1](#).

3.1. Data sources and data preprocessing

We used three datasets to form the basis for the FinnAffect corpus, consisting of the *Lahjoita Puhetta* (LP) (“donate speech”) corpus ([Moisio et al., 2022](#)), the Longitudinal Corpus of Finnish Spoken in Helsinki (*Helpuhe*, HP) ([University of Helsinki, 2014](#)) and the Longitudinal Corpus of Finnish Spoken in Tampere (*Tampuhe*, TP) ([Tampere University, 2023](#)).

LP is a crowdsourced dataset that contains speech from thousands of Finnish speakers who donated their speech samples for research purposes. The audio was recorded with the participants’ own computer or mobile device by using a software application that prompted the participants with a variety of different tasks and topics the participant could talk about. The dataset contains over 20,000 speakers from all age brackets and from all regions of Finland, covering different genders, dialects, and educational backgrounds. The speaker-specific metadata was collected directly from the participants and is included in the corpus. LP contains 3270 h of speech, out of which 1687 h have been transcribed for content. The audio quality varies from user to user, since the recording location, time, or device were not controlled in any way.

Fig. 1. A high-level description of the FinnAffect corpus creation.

Recording was possible with any device that supported the recording application. No objective audio quality measures are included in the corpus, but generally the audio quality is good, and the speech is clearly understandable, except for some outlier samples with disturbing distortions or other noise sources present in the recordings.

The HP and TP datasets are significantly smaller in size and different in nature compared to LP. They contain recordings of personal interviews collected in the 1970s, 1990s, and 2010s, with the original purpose of studying how spoken dialects change over time in the Helsinki and Tampere regions of Finland from a sociolinguistic perspective (see, e.g., Labov, 1994). The recordings were typically collected at the participants' homes, with changing levels of (non-disturbing) background noise audible. The earliest recordings were digitalized after the original recording session. However, the overall intelligibility of the speech in all recordings is good. The recordings contain speech from both interviewers and interviewees. The dialogue in the recordings has a free and relaxed form, in which the interviewees were asked about their past and present life experiences, as well as about their opinions on what the spoken language of their hometown is like and how it has changed over time. Even though different in the original size, all three datasets were evenly utilized in the sample selection process for annotation.

All three source corpora had transcribed and untranscribed portions of data, and we only used the transcribed sections for the FinnAffect corpus creation. LP transcriptions come time-aligned to the audio at the word level, whereas HP and TP transcriptions have a varying temporal resolution (from individual words and sentences to over one-minute-long stretches of speech). To represent all speech data in terms of utterance-sized samples, the audio and corresponding transcriptions were split into utterances using two different approaches depending on the dataset. Recordings in LP were split into utterances by using a silence criterion, where an utterance break was inserted whenever a silence of 300 ms or longer was observed between two consecutive words in a recording. For HP and TP, audio transcriptions of length 20 s or less were used as is. Longer stretches of audio were first force-aligned at the word level using the Aalto ASR forced alignment tool (Leinonen et al., 2021), after which the audio was split into utterances with the same silence criterion as with LP recordings.

To filter out low-quality speech samples, an automatic speech-to-noise (SNR) estimate was calculated for each speech sample using the Brouhaha model by Lavechin et al. (2023). Samples with at least 20 dB SNR and duration of 1–20 s were kept for further processing. This resulted in a total of 1,474,728 samples combined from the three source corpora (1,438,537, 26,407, and 9784 samples from LP, TP, and HP, respectively).

3.2. Sample selection for annotation

None of the source corpora contained any metadata or labels related to the potential presence of affect-rich speech in the samples. Given that a large proportion of spontaneous speech is expected to be relatively neutral in terms of affective content, we developed a pipeline for automatic sample selection to increase the affective diversity of samples chosen for annotation—an approach we refer to as *affect mining*.

The core idea of the pipeline is to represent the speech samples using a combination of a diverse set of features that are likely to be sensitive to different dimensions of affective expression in speech, as based on earlier research with affective language, and then use clustering-based AL to sample different parts of the resulting feature space. To this end, we utilized three complementary types of features to characterize the samples: (1) *general acoustic-prosodic features* optimized for affective analysis (88-dimensional eGeMAPSv02 feature set; Eyben et al. 2016) extracted at the utterance level using the openSMILE-toolkit (Eyben et al., 2010), (2) 6-dimensional output *posteriors* from a *pre-trained cross-linguistic speech emotion recognizer* ExHuBERT (Amiriparian et al., 2024a) trained on 119.5 h of affect-labeled speech from 37 datasets (not including Finnish), and (3) *text sentiment analysis posteriors* for three valence classes (negative, neutral, positive; a separate 0–1 posterior score for each) from a Finnsentiment model that is trained for sentiment analysis in Finnish using a large-scale text corpus extracted from social media site “Suomi24” (Lindén et al., 2023).

We z-score normalized the eGeMAPS features across each individual speaker to reduce the impact of speaker identity on feature variability. To reduce the dimensionality of the feature space, principal component analysis (PCA) was applied to the eGeMAPS features, keeping 42 dimensions that explained 90% of the variance of the original features.

To balance the variance contribution of each feature subset, the total variance of the resulting prosodic features, the ExHuBERT posteriors, and the text sentiment posteriors were each normalized separately to unit variance as described in Eq. (1), where X_i denotes the full set of data for each d_i -dimensional feature type i :

$$X_{i,\text{varnorm}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^{d_i} \sigma_k^2}} * X_i \quad (1)$$

Finally, the three types of feature vectors were then concatenated, forming a 51-dimensional feature representation for each utterance.

We aimed to mine affect-rich samples for annotation from the compiled dataset and to investigate whether our chosen sampling method would provide more diversity in the final annotations as opposed to random sampling. For affect mining, we used clustering-based AL. The entire data set was clustered into 1500 clusters using the CLARA algorithm (Kaufman and Rousseeuw, 2009) with a heuristic initialization implemented in Sckit-learn-extra (Pedregosa et al., 2011) and using cosine distance as the distance metric. The distance metric was chosen based on the results by Vaaras et al. (2022), who found the cosine distance to yield the best results on high-dimensional data when simulating medoid-based AL for selecting samples for annotation and consequent SER system deployment. A total of 9000 samples were then selected based on the clustering, where six samples were selected from each cluster by always selecting the cluster medoid and its five closest samples (using the cosine distance metric). When choosing the nearest samples, a constraint was used to choose two samples from all three source corpora (LP, HP, and TP), provided that the cluster had enough samples from each source. Lacking samples were selected randomly from other clusters so that the target sample count was achieved. In addition to clustering-based samples, 3000 samples were selected by randomly sampling from the full pool of source utterances. This was done to obtain a representative distribution of affective content from the source corpora, and to enable comparison against the affect mining approach.

3.3. Annotation process

Five Finnish native speakers with self-reported normal hearing (three female, aged 20–30) were hired to annotate the samples. All recruits were students of Tampere University with no previous experience in linguistics or audio-analysis. The combined set of 12,000 samples was randomly shuffled, and then 4000 samples were assigned to each annotator. Of those, 2000 were common to all annotators, and 2000 were unique to each annotator. An additional 20 randomly chosen samples (common to all annotators) were selected to serve as quality assurance samples, which were used to follow the consistency of each annotator as they progressed with their work. The quality assurance samples were divided into sets of five samples that were annotated three times in random order within a batch of 1015 subsequent samples. Overall, this resulted in a total of 4060 samples to annotate per one annotator. The annotators were given one month of time to perform the annotations and were financially rewarded for each batch of 1015 annotated samples delivered.

A training session of approximately two hours was arranged for the annotators, which contained a theoretical section and a practical section. The general scope of the larger research project (human and machine perception of affect in speech) was covered as well as the nature of the used datasets (i.e., LP, HP, and TP). The annotators were explained how human annotations are generally used in signal processing and machine learning, and they were explained that they were to provide continuous ratings for valence and arousal (*tunnesävy* and *virittyneisyys* in Finnish), as based on the circumplex model of affect by Russell et al. (1989), which is often used in describing the range of human emotions as well as the affective properties of language (e.g., Sianipar et al., 2016).

Since one of the purposes of the present corpus is enabling the study of the different factors behind affective expression in Finnish, the annotators were not instructed to analytically focus on any specific aspects of the samples. In contrast, the annotators were instructed to use their initial intuitive interpretation of the auditory experience during the rating process, focusing on the most predominant impressions in the valence and arousal dimensions. It was clearly underlined that there were no right or wrong answers when performing the task. The instructions aimed to ensure that the annotators would not develop explicit (and hence potentially artificially biased) strategies for the annotation. They were also instructed to do the annotations using the supplied headphones and to do the work in a calm environment in a situation when they were able to listen with focus and intent. During the training session, the annotators were guided through the annotation process as well as the use of the annotation tool by configuring the annotation environment on their personal computers provided to them, finally annotating a set of 50 samples during the session (same samples shared by all annotators and not included in the final set of 4060 annotated samples). The annotation results of the training session were not shared with the annotators.

The annotation was conducted using a graphical user interface (GUI) implemented in Python. The annotation scheme was as follows: the annotators were played assigned samples of 1–20 s. Each sample consisted of a short, up to 4 s of preceding context followed by the actual target sample audio to be annotated. The context was clearly distinguishable from the target sample with a notable increase in volume from the context to the target, implemented as a linear volume ramp that had a maximum level of -10.45 dB (relative to the signal), after which the signal level jumped to 0 dB. The annotators could listen to each sample a maximum of two times, after which they gave the score for both valence and arousal using sliders that had a floating-point scale from -1.0 (negative valence and low arousal) to 1.0 (positive valence and high arousal). In addition, the annotators could tag the audio quality of the listened sample as bad quality, in case the intelligibility of the sample was disturbingly bad.

Annotators were enforced to do the annotations in 30-minute or shorter sessions, as the tool forced the user to take a 15-minute break after each 30 min of use. The annotators were agnostic to all metadata related to the samples, including whether the samples were based on AL or random selection. All annotators delivered annotations for all the samples that were assigned to them.

3.4. Corpus description

The resulting FinnAffect corpus consists of 12,000 annotated samples, with 4028 samples originating from LP, 2577 from TP, and 2395 from HP. As described before, a set of 2000 samples was annotated by all five annotators. We refer to this subset as the gold standard (GS) set, as it establishes a robust reference for affective content in the data, although the annotation score distributions were qualitatively similar between the GS set and the 10,000 samples with only one annotation each. In this section, we examine the agreement rates between the annotators within the continuous label space as well as in a discretized label space. In addition, we will describe the statistical properties of the corpus and evaluate the used sampling methods for the annotated samples.

While the annotation scores between annotators correlated moderately even without any processing steps, there were noticeable differences in the use of the annotation scale between annotators. For this reason, we first normalized the annotations of each annotator to have zero mean and unit variance, rescaling the combined set of annotations to the original scale of $[-1.0, 1.0]$. This increased the inter-annotator agreements in both valence and arousal without affecting the relative ratings of each annotator. The use of the annotation scale as well as the variation between the annotators before and after annotation normalization for GS samples is visualized in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The distribution of valence (top) and arousal (bottom) annotation scores on the GS set. The data is shown before (blue) and after (red) the annotator-specific normalization of the scoring scales. Solid lines denote the mean score across all the annotators, and shading shows the standard deviation of scores across the annotators. Samples have been sorted on the x-axis according to their mean score. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 1

The discretization thresholds for the continuous valued labels, x denotes the annotation value.

Dim	High	Neutral	Low
Valence	$x \geq 0.08$	$-0.07 \leq x \leq 0.07$	$x \leq -0.08$
Arousal	$x > 0$	-	$x \leq 0$

To support classification experiments with the data, we also discretized the continuous labels to categorical ones. For arousal, we divided the data into low and high arousal, whereas valence was categorized into negative, neutral, or positive, to enable representation of neutral emotional content and thereby following the practice of Amiriparian et al. (2024a) in their SER experiments. The discretization thresholds applied to the continuous scores are described in Table 1. These thresholds were automatically optimized so that they maximized inter-annotator agreement on the resulting discretized labels, as measured with the mean Cohen’s kappa score between the mode of all annotations and the labels from each individual annotator.

We measured the inter-annotator agreement in both the continuous annotation space and in a discretized label space. For the continuous valued annotations, we used Spearman’s correlation to measure agreement rates between individual annotators and the mean score over all five annotation scores per sample. The mean correlation coefficient between each annotator and the mean score of all annotators was $\rho_{mean} = 0.856$ for valence and $\rho_{mean} = 0.898$ for arousal. The mean annotator-to-annotator correlation coefficient was $\rho = 0.422$ for valence and $\rho = 0.566$ for arousal. The Spearman’s correlation matrix between the annotator pairs and the annotation mean is shown in Fig. 3. Inter-annotator agreement in the discrete label space was measured with pairwise Cohen’s kappa (Cohen, 1960; Pedregosa et al., 2011) between all annotators (Fig. 4) and the mode of all annotations, as well as the Fleiss’ kappa (Fleiss, 1971; Seabold and Perktold, 2010) among all five annotators. The resulting Fleiss’ kappa scores were $\kappa_{fleiss} = 0.248$ for valence and $\kappa_{fleiss} = 0.395$ for arousal, whereas the mean Cohen’s kappa between all annotators and the annotation mode was $\kappa_{mode\ cohen} = 0.520$ for valence and $\kappa_{mode\ cohen} = 0.638$ for arousal. The mean annotator-to-annotator kappa was $\kappa_{cohen} = 0.253$ for valence and $\kappa_{cohen} = 0.399$ for arousal. The agreement levels are similar to those in Vaaras et al. (2021) (who obtained 0.48 and 0.28 Fleiss’ kappa scores for valence and arousal, respectively), who had three expert annotators scoring high and low arousal scores and positive and non-positive valence scores (binary labeling for both dimensions) for their

Table 2

The specifics of the annotated samples in the FinnAffect corpus. The gender information of the speaker is procured from the metadata of each source dataset; U means unknown.

The FinnAffect corpus		
Feature	Quantity	Unit
Samples	12,000	utterance
Speakers	3936	-
Speaker gender	3902/6425/1673	M/F/U
Total audio duration	13.42	h
Sample length	4.02/2.71	s, mean/std
Continuous valence (unnormalized)	0.05/0.16	mean/std
Continuous arousal (unnormalized)	-0.13/0.25	mean/std
Continuous valence (normalized)	0.00/0.11	mean/std
Continuous arousal (normalized)	0.00/0.20	mean/std
Discrete valence	2741/7178/2081	low/neu/high
Discrete arousal	5685/6315	low/high

data collected in a hospital environment. In our study, the annotators had higher agreement ratings in the arousal scores than valence scores in both continuous and discrete label spaces. Overall, the annotators consistently had moderate to high agreement rates with the mean and mode annotations (i.e., individual annotators agreed with the average opinion), whereas the agreements between individual annotators varied more.

Finally, to analyze the benefit of the AL-based sample selection, we compared the distributions of the annotation scores between samples selected using the two different sample selection methods described in Section 3.1. The comparisons were conducted within annotation scores of each individual annotator as well as the mean scores of both the complete set and the GS subset. The distributions of mean scores across all annotators for both valence and arousal scores and for both sampling methods are visualized in Fig. 5. First, the annotation distributions were compared by computing the differences in standard deviation of annotation scores between randomly selected samples and clustering based samples. No conclusive differences were found in the standard deviations of annotation scores between the two different subsets of samples. Furthermore, we compared the variances of the randomly sampled set and the clustering based set with Levene’s test (Levene, 1960) and found no statistically significant differences for either of the affect dimensions ($p > 0.05$ for both valence and arousal).

The descriptive statistics of the final corpus are shown in Table 2, where the annotation score metrics are based on the mean (for continuous annotations) and mode (for discrete labels) of the scores among all annotations.

To summarize, the collected annotations showed moderate to high average agreement between the five annotators in both arousal and valence domains, with scores having approximately unimodal and semi-symmetrical distributions around neutral (i.e., zero score for both valence and arousal), as expected for spontaneous speech data. The AL approach did not produce any conclusive differences in affective score distributions compared to random sampling when selecting samples for annotation from the large-scale speech corpora. However, in light of the inter-annotator agreement scores as well as the variability within the annotation score distributions (with distributions clearly spreading around zero within the annotation range), the sampling method paired with the annotation scheme produced a collection of speech samples with affective annotations that can be used in further studies of affect in Finnish.

4. Speech emotion recognition experiments

To test the feasibility of the annotations and the usability of the corpus in SER tasks, we performed classification and regression experiments using both the discretized labels and the mean continuous

Fig. 3. Inter-annotator Spearman correlations for normalized valence (right) and arousal (left) scores on the GS set. Mean refers to the arithmetic mean score calculated across all the annotators.

Fig. 4. Inter-annotator Cohen's kappa scores for discretized GS sample annotations. Mode refers to the label that appears most often in the set of annotations for a sample.

Fig. 5. The mean distributions of annotation scores from the GS set for clustering and random selection-based samples. The distributions are plotted with 100 bins and normalized to make the distribution comparison clearer. The original sample counts for the distributions are $N = 1500$ for clustering based samples and $N = 500$ for random sampling-based samples.

valued valence and arousal scores. The aim of the experiments was to get further information on the systematicity of the affective contents and their labels in the dataset, and thereby to also test the applicability of the corpus for future speech affect and SER research in Finnish.

4.1. Classifiers, regression models, and features

We compared two algorithms for classification of ternary valence and binary arousal: an SVM classifier (Pedregosa et al., 2011) and the ExHuBERT (Amiriparian et al., 2024a,b) model with and without fine-tuning. For predicting continuous-valued valence and arousal scores, a support vector regression algorithm (SVR) (Pedregosa et al., 2011) was used as the baseline model. We also employed a WavLM-based model (“MSP-baseline”) that was originally trained on MSP-Podcast corpus and used as the baseline system in the Odyssey 2024 Emotion Recognition competition (O24) (Goncalves et al., 2024c,b,a). The model was tested with and without fine-tuning on the current FinnAffect corpus.

For training and testing the SVM and SVR algorithms, we used the eGeMAPSv02 feature set together with ExHuBERT and Finnsentiment posteriors (Eyben et al., 2016; Amiriparian et al., 2024a; Lindén et al., 2023) concatenated into one 97 dimensional feature vector. Both the training and testing data were z-score normalized using the mean and standard deviation computed from the training set. For training and testing the ExHuBERT model, we used the raw waveforms of the audio samples with three second windowing applied to the utterances. As for the MSP-baseline experiments, we did not modify the model from its original configuration. The default configuration, as shared by the authors of the models (Goncalves et al., 2024a,b) sets the maximum

Table 3

The data split specifications describing the distribution of valence and arousal labels as well as speaker- and sample-related statistical properties for the GS and train data splits used in the SER experiments.

Training (GS) and testing data split			
Feature	GS	Train	Unit
Speakers	828	3108	–
Genders	675/1069/256	786/2240/1037	M/F/U
Samples	2000	4063	utterance
Sample length	4.09/2.87	2.90/1.70	s, mean/std
Discrete valence	423/1311/266	827/2491/745	low/neut/high
Discrete arousal	953/1047	1889/2174	low/high
Continuous valence	0.00/0.08	0.00/0.09	mean/std
Continuous arousal	0.00/0.16	0.00/0.19	mean/std

length of the input audio to 192000 samples, which with the sampling rate of the FinnAffect samples (16 kHz) means the samples were truncated to the length of 12 s during inference. When fine-tuning, the input length was increased to 20 s to accommodate for the maximum audio duration of the FinnAffect corpus, as this was observed to improve performance compared to fine-tuning with 12-second inputs.

4.2. Experimental setup

The SER experiments were conducted as follows. For the classification tasks, we trained two SVM classifiers for both target dimensions separately (binary classification for arousal and ternary classification for valence). In the experiments using the ExHuBERT model, we had a classification scheme that combines both low and high arousal as well as low, neutral, and high valence predictions into one six-dimensional output vector (the six unique valence-arousal pairs), as done in the original paper by Amiriparian et al. (2024a). Classifier performance was measured using the unweighted average recall (UAR), similar to Vaaras et al. (2021), Amiriparian et al. (2024a). Similarly for the regression task, we trained separate SVR models for predicting continuous affective scores for arousal and valence. In the experiments using the MSP-baseline models, the ground truth scores were rescaled to the range [0.0, 1.0] to match the baseline model’s design. The regression performance was measured using the concordance correlation coefficient (CCC) to align with the O24 competition (Goncalves et al., 2024c).

The GS set was used as the test set for all experiments. The rest of the annotated samples were used for training and validation after removing all samples from speakers that were also included in the GS set, as speaker dependencies between train and test can inflate SER results substantially. This reduced the total number of training samples to 4063 utterances. A summary of the data split is shown in Table 3.

For monitoring and early-stopping the ExHuBERT and the MSP-baseline fine-tuning processes, the non-GS utterances were randomly split into separate training and validation sets with a 0.8 to 0.2 ratio. The validation set was used for testing the model in between epochs. The validation performance was tracked throughout model training, and the model with the highest performance score was stored and used for testing.

4.2.1. Classifier parameter selection

For the SVM, a grid search was performed with different SVM hyperparameters with a five-fold cross-validation (i.e., 0.8 to 0.2 training and validation split with each fold used for validation once) training (utilizing the Scikit-learn Python library) to find the best performing classifiers. We tested linear, polynomial, RBF, and sigmoid kernels with different regularization (C) and box-constraint (gamma) parameters. For the multi-class valence classification task, we also compared One-Versus-One (OVO) and One-Versus-Rest (OVR) decision function shapes. The resulting best hyperparameters corresponded to C=1 with

the linear kernel function (gamma constraint not used with linear kernels). The same hyperparameter configuration yielded the best results for both arousal and valence. OVO decision function shape performed better than OVR in the valence classification task.

Separate classifiers were trained for predicting the arousal and valence labels in all cases. For the ExHuBERT experiments, the classifier was trained to predict low and high arousal together with low, neutral, and high valences as a 6-dimensional combinatory posterior vector (as done by Amiriparian et al. 2024a). Separate valence and arousal UARs were calculated from this combinatory posterior vector in both training and testing phases.

As reported by Amiriparian et al. (2024a), the ExHuBERT model performs best with three second audio windows. For this reason, the utterances used in training and testing the ExHuBERT model were first split into three second windows with 50% overlap between consecutive windows. Window mean was used for padding samples shorter than three seconds. The corresponding utterance-level label was assigned to the windowed samples. During testing, the mean of class posteriors across all the 3-s windows of an utterance was calculated before choosing the arg max of the resulting posterior.

The ExHuBERT experiments were conducted using the model provided by the authors via Hugging Face (Amiriparian et al., 2024b). In the fine-tuning experiment, the model was trained for 100 epochs using cross-entropy loss and AdamW optimizer with a 10^{-5} learning rate with otherwise default parameters for the optimizer implementation as implemented in the used PyTorch (Paszke et al., 2019) library. The best models (to be used for the GS tests) were chosen across all the training epochs for valence and arousal based on the models’ UAR score on the validation data. The aforementioned ExHuBERT hyperparameters for the fine-tuning were chosen based on the examples provided by the authors in the Hugging Face model card.

4.2.2. Regression model parameter selection

The SVR hyperparameters were selected based on a similar grid search process as for the SVM classifier by comparing the validation set performance with linear, polynomial, RBF and sigmoid kernels along with different regularization (C) and box-constraint (gamma) parameters. The resulting best hyperparameters for predicting arousal corresponded to C=1 with the RBF kernel using the box-constraint $\gamma_{arousal}$ described in Eq. (2), which is the default gamma parameter for the SVR implementation in the Scikit-learn Python library. As for valence, the selected hyperparameters were C=10, the RBF kernel, and the box-constraint $\gamma_{valence}$ described in Eq. (3).

$$\gamma_{arousal} = \frac{1}{N_{features} * \sigma_{training data}^2} \quad (2)$$

$$\gamma_{valence} = \frac{1}{N_{features}} \quad (3)$$

The MSP-baseline experiments were conducted using the models and configurations provided by the authors of the O24 competition (Goncalves et al., 2024a,b). In the fine-tuning experiment, the

Fig. 6. Normalized confusion matrices of the best performing classifier predictions in the SER experiments. Ground truth on the y-axis and predicted label on the x-axis. Valence is predicted by an SVM classifier, and arousal is predicted by the fine-tuned ExHuBERT model. Valence on the left, arousal on the right.

Table 4

Mean UAR results for valence and arousal classification predictions using the FinnAffect GS samples. The best performance levels are bolded.

Classification experiment mean UARs		
Classifier	Valence	Arousal
SVM	0.461	0.690
ExHuBERT	0.388	0.603
ExHuBERT	0.399	0.719
fine-tuned		

model was trained for 10 epochs using a CCC-based loss function (Eq. (4)):

$$\mathcal{L}_{O24\text{ competition}} = 1 - CCC, \quad (4)$$

as applied in the O24 competition, and with AdamW optimizer with a 10^{-5} learning rate. The models with the best validation set performance during the fine-tuning were saved and tested on the GS data.

4.3. Results and comparison to existing work

The results of the classification experiments are presented in Table 4. All classifier configurations achieved higher than chance-level prediction performance (0.333 for valence and 0.500 for arousal). The fine-tuned ExHuBERT model performed best in predicting arousal with a UAR of 0.719, while the SVM classifier performed best in predicting valence, reaching a UAR of 0.458. Confusion matrices for the best performing classifier predictions are shown in Fig. 6.

The results are on par with the results achieved by Vaaras et al. (2023), who achieved an average UAR of 0.734 for binary valence (negative + neutral vs. positive) and 0.732 for binary arousal (low vs. high) using spontaneous Finnish from a neonatal hospital environment.

Since a large proportion of the available speech emotion datasets contain acted data and usually have speech samples labeled in discrete emotion classes (e.g., sadness, happiness, anger, and neutral) as opposed to discrete valence and arousal classes (Rathi and Tripathy, 2024; George and Muhamed Ilyas, 2024), direct comparison of achieved classification performances using the most studied speech emotion datasets to results gained in this study is difficult. However, on a general level, the reported classification results can be examined in a broader SER context. For example, the authors of ExHuBERT tested their model against several publicly available speech emotion datasets with cross-linguistic samples (Amiriparian et al., 2024a), using the combinatory (valence and arousal predicted at the same time) 6-dimensional classification scheme, and achieved an average UAR of 0.697 over all corpora tested, with a UAR of as high as 0.991 when testing with acted speech data from the EMO-DB dataset (Burkhardt et al., 2005).

The results of the regression experiments are presented in Table 5. The fine-tuned MSP-baseline model had the best performance for both valence and arousal, with a noticeable improvement when comparing

Table 5

The CCC results for valence and arousal regression predictions using the FinnAffect GS samples. The best performance levels are bolded.

Regression experiment CCC scores		
Regression model	Valence	Arousal
SVR	0.156	0.548
MSP-baseline	0.150	0.369
MSP-baseline	0.270	0.689
fine-tuned		

to the MSP-baseline model without fine-tuning. The SVR algorithm outperformed the untrained MSP-baseline model in predicting both dimensions, but fell far behind the fine-tuned MSP-baseline in regression accuracy.

For comparison, in the O24 competition, the single-task development and test set CCC scores for the MSP-baseline were 0.709 and 0.607 for valence, respectively, (Goncalves et al., 2024b). The corresponding arousal scores were 0.651 and 0.566 for the development and test sets, respectively, (Goncalves et al., 2024a). In our experiments the valence prediction performance is significantly lower than for the O24 competition benchmark. However, the performance increase following the MSP-baseline fine-tuning indicates that there are learnable valence related signals in the FinnAffect data even in the acoustic signal without a language-specific model capable of understanding the linguistic content. In the arousal prediction task the MSP-baseline model performed better, achieving even higher performance levels than the O24 competition benchmarks after fine-tuning.

Overall, the SER results suggest that the FinnAffect corpus provides a solid basis for studying affect in Finnish speech, for which spontaneous data is especially needed, also expanding the currently limited set of affective speech corpora for agglutinative languages. The annotated data is consistent enough that predictive models can be trained using the corpus, even though the annotators are less mutually in agreement compared to, for example, acted speech. Hence, the introduced corpus works as the needed stepping stone for further studying the affective properties of spontaneous Finnish.

5. Discussion

This study introduced the first large-scale affective speech corpus based on spontaneous Finnish. The aim was to create a large spontaneous speech corpus with annotations describing the affective dimensions of the speech and to test the feasibility of the corpus for affective research in terms of annotation consistency analysis and SER experiments.

As a methodological contribution, we also studied a clustering-based AL method for automatic data sampling for annotation from a large unannotated set of speech samples, where the attempt was to mine a more expressively diverse set of speech samples in opposition to pure random sampling.

The introduced corpus (FinnAffect) contains 12,000 spontaneous speech samples with continuous-valued annotation scores in the arousal and valence domain marked by five human annotators. The data sampling as well as the data annotation process was successful in that sense, that all annotators were able to finish all the sample annotations allocated to them with good consistency with themselves as well as in comparison to the other annotators. The conducted SER experiments support the conclusion that the sampled speech, together with the human annotations, provides feasible data for modeling and further study of affective properties in spontaneous spoken language in general and in Finnish in particular.

As for the AL-based approach, there were no significant differences in the annotation score distributions compared to random sampling, suggesting that the expressive diversity within the AL-sampled speech is comparable to that in random sampling. Since the random sampling can be considered as representative of everyday speech, the AL outcome should also thereby reflect general tendencies of spontaneous Finnish in the source corpora. While there are already some cases of extreme affective expression (e.g., very low or high arousal or valence), greater quantities of samples representing the low and high ends of the affective continuums would be beneficial for further SER development and affective language research.

There are several potential reasons for why the affect mining approach did not result in greater diversity of affective content. First, it is possible that the lack of farthest-first traversal (FAFT) initialization (Gonzalez, 1985) for the CLARA-based clustering, as used by Vaaras et al. (2023), resulted in a clustering outcome where cluster centroids are distributed according to the overall data density in the feature space. If so, this would mean that samples in the outskirts of the feature space, i.e., samples that might consist of less frequent yet distinct affective expression, were not proportionally more represented in the clustering outcomes than what results from random (=density based) sampling. In our study, the medoids were initialized using a heuristic method that finds the N (N being the defined number of medoids, in our case $N = 1500$) data points that have the smallest distance to every other point in the set of samples (Pedregosa et al., 2011).

Additionally, CLARA is designed for clustering large datasets on which the use of the original K-medoids algorithm is not computationally plausible. For this reason, CLARA clusters the data in randomly chosen, iteratively smaller subsets of data instead of looking at the entire feature space at once. This local optimization might also contribute to the lack of differences in annotation scores between random sampling and AL-based samples. Third, since we used different features to represent our data compared to Vaaras et al. (2022), it is possible that the utilized cosine distance is not ideal for the current signal features where two thirds of the data correspond to posteriors from classifiers.

Finally, the typical way of selecting samples in clustering based AL is to set the number of clusters based on the annotation budget (i.e., the number of samples that are afforded to annotate), the idea being that the cluster centers (medoids in our used method) are chosen for annotation and assumed to be *the most representative* sample of the cluster in the chosen feature representation. The clustering computation time of CLARA increases rapidly with larger medoid counts, which is why we chose to cluster the data into 1500 medoids and also take their five nearest samples instead of directly clustering the data into 9000 clusters of our target annotation budget. By limiting the number of clusters, the selected samples might not be as diversely representative of different speech phenomena compared to using only cluster medoids.

To shed more light on the issue, we conducted a series of posthoc tests to analyze the effect of different clustering algorithm implementations and cluster initializations using the annotated set of 12,000 samples of FinnAffect (see also Lahtinen et al., 2025). We used the affect mining approach described in Section 3.2 on the 12,000 samples and simulated the sample selection and annotation process by

choosing different numbers of samples for annotation and by using the actual annotation scores for the samples chosen in process. By using variance of valence and arousal scores across the “annotated” samples as a measure of sample diversity, we learned that the lack of FAFT initialization in the clustering process causes the annotation score diversity to converge to a similar outcome than what is obtained by random sampling. In contrast, by choosing the samples with FAFT directly, or by applying k-medoids clustering initialized with FAFT, a more diverse set of samples could be obtained for both valence and arousal dimensions. Hence, based on the simulations with this more limited set of samples, the reason for similar annotation scores for our affect mining approach and random sampling appeared to be driven by the lack of sufficiently diverse initialization for the clustering process—a consequence of poor computational scaling of the standard k-medoids and the limited support for CLARA initialization methods in the Scikit Python library. As long as the clustering initialization can be performed with FAFT, the affect mining process appears to provide more diverse samples compared to random sampling.

6. Conclusions

The subjective and language-dependent nature of affective expression in speech calls for representative speech data to push the boundaries of linguistic research and SER development in different domains. The FinnAffect corpus now provides a means for working towards these goals in spontaneous Finnish speech, consisting of affect-labeled speech from speakers of various ages, genders, and dialects from different parts of Finland. Despite the ambivalent findings from the AL-based affect mining, the methods we used for sampling and annotating utterances from a large pool of unscripted and unannotated speech data may also prove useful for other speech researchers working with corpus development.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kalle Lahtinen: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Liisa Mustanoja:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Okko Räsänen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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We would like to thank the annotators for their contributions to this study. The program code and extracted feature sets used in the experiments are available at <https://github.com/SPEECHCOG/AffectClassification/>. The FinnAffect corpus (audio samples, metadata, affective labels and transcriptions) will be available in the Language Bank of Finland at <https://urn.fi/urn:nbn:fi:lb-2025081821>, including the annotated samples and their continuous scores and discrete labels. The corpus also includes the remaining 1.4M unannotated samples processed with the same pre-processing pipeline and with the propagated cluster labels, and to enable future expansion of the corpus with new annotations.

Data availability

Scripts and features of reported experiments are available at <https://github.com/SPEECHCOG/AffectClassification/>. The corpus will be released through The Language Bank of Finland (<https://urn.fi/urn:nbn:fi:lb-2025081821>).

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